

Colibrys Accelerometers

Commissioning and software

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1. Introduction

The MS9002 is a fully calibrated bulk capacitive accelerometer, specially designed for high performance inertial measurements. Accelerometer long term bias repeatability and stability, robustness up to 6000g and low power are adapted for overall inertial requirements, even in harsh environments. The sensor is packaged in a 20-pin LCC ceramic housing, thus ensuring a full hermeticity.

2. Features

2.1 Sensor Range

The sensor measuring range varies between -2g and +2g. The corresponding outputted voltage varies from 0 to 5 V, by an applied supply voltage of 5V. Following figure shows the characteristic curve.

Figure 1 Sensor range

2.2 Reference system

The sensor measures accelerations along one single axis. The measured axis is the i(z) one, pointing out from sensor, in the position indicated by the drawing

The packaging is a standard LCC ceramic housing with a total of 20 pins. The outline of the LCC20 ceramic package and the Center of Gravity (CG) is illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 2 Package mechanical dimensions

3. Electrical integration in the system

3.1 Safran suggestions for the electrical integration

Source: SVN\posctrl_slungloads\trunk\09_Sensors\Colibrys\Technical-training-MS9000_2.pdf

BASIC ELECTRICAL INTEGRATION IN SYSTEM

Electrical integration

The sensor integration involves an electronic design and a mechanical aspect.

The electronic design is mainly viewed as 2 stages which are the sensors with basic required elements and the application oriented to one of domain TILT, INERTIAL, VIBRATION.

The mechanical aspect is about handling to assure performance and reliability of the sensor.

BASIC ELECTRICAL INTEGRATION IN SYSTEM

Electrical integration

1- Power must be very stable and low noise

2- Sensors requires 3 capacitors 1uF X7R

3- filter to be inserted with the cutting frequency as low as possible in accordance with application.

Pin	MS9000 Description	Notes
4	VDD	Power supply
5	VDDND	Accelerometer output reference voltage (VDD / 2)
6	VSS	Ground
7	VD	Temperature sensor output
8	Vout	Accelerometer output signal
16	VFP (Colibrys internal calibration pin)	Must be connected to VSS
17	SCK (Colibrys internal calibration pin)	Must be connected to VSS
18	SDA (Colibrys internal calibration pin)	Must be connected to VSS

COLIBRYS PRODUCT ELECTRICAL INTEGRATION IN SYSTEM

Why a low pass filter on Vout?
Switched capacitors introduce spikes on output voltage as presented on the next graph:

+
No spikes using
VS1000.A

Temperature sensor is LM20 and manufacturer preconizes applying one low pass filter to reduce noise on Vo.

BASIC ELECTRICAL INTEGRATION IN SYSTEM

Electrical integration

INERTIAL or TILT

- Low bandwidth (~ 100Hz)
- Temperature compensation
- Non-linearity compensation

4- Digitalization frequency must be at least 4 times the cutting frequency value of filter. Due to ratiometry, the ADC must be ratiometric too.

5- Processing in view to apply treatment of information like compensation

4. Power Supply

We tested the performances of the sensor with different power supplies:

- Laboratory power supply
- Power Supply from Raspberry Pi
- Power Bank
- Batteries

Figure 3 Power supply output

It can be clearly seen how the power supply coming from the raspberry pi ADC Board as well as from a laboratory power supply has big spikes. Power bank power supply is better, but best results are obtained with the battery. It will be therefore needed to supply sensors with a battery, in order to have a stable power supply.

5. Evolution board for Colibrys

Pinout Description

Pin	Description	Notes
4	VDD	Power supply
5	VMID	Accelerometer output reference voltage (VDD / 2)
6	VSS	Ground
7	VO	Temperature sensor output
8	Vout	Accelerometer output signal
16	VPP (Safran Colibrys internal calibration pin)	Must be connected to VSS
17	SCK (Safran Colibrys internal calibration pin)	Must be connected to VSS
18	SDA (Safran Colibrys internal calibration pin)	Must be connected to VSS

Figure 4 Pinout description

Figure 5 Proximity circuit

Vcc	Rot
Vss (GND)	Blau
Vout	Grau
Vmid	Gelb
VO	Grün
NC	Braun

Evolution board was suggested as compact solution, where to integrate the accelerometer. It has also three required 1uF capacitors for the power supply, as suggested by Safran.

6. Low Pass Filter

Not using a low-pass filter on the output signal led to the above described spikes, which we could see in our measurements. We therefore realized a low pass filter with a bandwidth of 270 Hz, by adding a resistor and a capacitor at the output signal. The difference between the two signals, without and with low-pass filter can be clearly seen in the following images.

Figure 6 Colibrays sensor and board used for tests

Figure 7 Sensor signal with spikes

7. ADC converter and Raspberry Pi

Figure 8 High-precision AD/DA Board

7.1 Features

The High-Precision AD/DA Board allows you to add high-precision AD/DA functions to the Raspberry Pi. These are the most relevant features:

- Onboard ADS1256, 8ch 24bit high-precision ADC (4ch differential input), 30ksps sampling rate
- Onboard DAC8532, 2ch 16bit high-precision DAC
- Onboard input interface via pinheaders, for connecting analog signal the pinout is compatible with Waveshare sensor interface standard, easy to connect various analog sensor modules
- Onboard input/output interface via screw terminals, for connecting analog/digital signal

7.2 Measuring resolution

VDD (Supply Voltage)	5	V	
Vss (GND)	0	V	
Acc Range	4	g	(+/-2 g)
Resolution	0.0001	g	(0.1 mg)
K1 (Sensitivity)	1	V/g	

Ai (Acceleration)	-2	g	
Vout	0.5	V	(0.5 <-> 4.5 V)

Vout min	0.5	V	
Vout max	4.5	V	
Vout range	4	V	
ADC Resolution	24	bit	
Voltage Resolution	2.38419E-07	V	
Acc Meas Resolution	2.38419E-07	g	
Acc Meas Resolution	2.3365E-06	m/s ²	

7.3 Settings and connections

Figure 9 Raspberry pi with AD/DA Precision Board

- Connect the high-precision AD-DA Board to the Raspberry Pi
- Jumper settings:
 - Connect the two pins 5V -> Vcc to set the power supply to 5V
 - Connect the two pins 5V -> VREF to set the power supply to 5V
 - No connection between ADJ and AD0 (sets potentiometer as analog input)
 - No connection between LDR and AD1 (sets LDR to analog input)
 - Connect pins AINCOM - AGND to get Single Ended Signals
Or, **do not connect Jumper AINCOM - AGND to get Differential Signals**
- If using differential signals:
 - Use AIN0 to AIN7, preferably adjacent inputs
 - Do not use AINCOM
- Leave any unused analog inputs floating. This minimizes input leakage current.
- On the software, several parameters can be set, depending on the kind of measurement (single ended – differential), acquisition speed, etc.

8. Software for reading analog data

8.1 Proposed Software

The proposed software is the BCM2835 and ADS1256 library:

- Link Wiki AD/DA Board: https://www.waveshare.com/wiki/High-Precision_AD/DA_Board
- Github Repository: <https://github.com/waveshare/High-Precision-AD-DA-Board>

The test program gave problem with received data.

Figure 10 Received data (many wrong zero values)

As you can see from the picture, many output data were zero. A first analysis on the code suggested us to search for other solutions.

8.2 Used software

This is the server code for the Waveshare High-Precision AD/DA Board using Wiring Pi instead of the bcm2835 library. This software uses 'Wiring Pi' <http://wiringpi.com/reference/setup/>.

- Link: https://github.com/ferbar/raspberry_ads1256_dac8552
- Required:
 - Install Libboost
sudo apt-get install libboost1.67-all-dev (check versions with 'TAB')
 - Enable SPI Interface on Raspberry Pi
Menu -> Einstellungen -> Raspberry-Pi Konfiguration -> Schnittstellen

The adapted software used for the project is saved in the github repository under the folder 'raspberrypi_colibrys'.

8.3 Timing performance outputting one channel

According to datasheets and company suggestions, the digitalization frequency must be at least 4 times the cutting frequency value of filter (about 70-100 Hz).

To measure the time taken for a one channel measurement of the ADC, following code was used:

```

clock_t begin = clock();
ADS1256_lock();
ADS1256_WaitDRDY();
digitalWrite(ADS1256_CS, LOW); // pi.write(22, 0) # ADS1256 /CS low

// Get data Channel 1 - Differential: AinP = AIN0, AinN = AIN1 -> p | n -> 0000 0001
unsigned char databyte[6] = {{CMD_WREG | REG_MUX}, '\x00', (unsigned char) (0 << 4 | 1),
CMD_SYNC, CMD_WAKEUP, CMD_RDATA};
...
write(spiHandle, databyte, 6);

ADS1256_DelayDATA();
int count=read(spiHandle, databyte, 3);

digitalWrite(ADS1256_CS, HIGH); // pi.write(22, 1) # ADS1256 /CS high
int data = (databyte[0]<<16 | databyte[1]<<8 | databyte[2]);
ADCbuffer[bufferPos].time = getCurrentTime(); // system time, no monotonic. do not use for dt.
ADCbuffer[bufferPos].value[channel] = data;
double volt = ((double)data / 0x7ffff) *5;
channel++;
if(channel>=cfg_max_channels) {
channel=0;
bufferPos++;
if(bufferPos >= maxBufferEntries) {
bufferPos=0;
}
}
ADS1256_unlock();
clock_t end = clock();
double time_spent = (double)(end - begin) / CLOCKS_PER_SEC;
printf("%f, %01.4f \n", time_spent,volt); // output on terminal!

```


Figure 11 Delta time of data acquisition

From the graphic it is possible to see that the time needed is maximum 0.5 ms, which corresponds to 2000 Hz, which is higher than the required 100Hz * 4.

8.4 Settings to measure differential signals

On the board, the pin selection is controlled by multiplexer register, in order to define Ain positive, Ain negative, etc..

MUX : Input Multiplexer Control Register (Address 01h)

Reset Value = 01h

BIT 7	BIT 6	BIT 5	BIT 4	BIT 3	BIT 2	BIT 1	BIT 0
PSEL3	PSEL2	PSEL1	PSEL0	NSEL3	NSEL2	NSEL1	NSEL0

Bits 7-4 **PSEL3, PSEL2, PSEL1, PSEL0**: Positive Input Channel (AIN_P) Select

0000 = AIN0 (default)

0001 = AIN1

0010 = AIN2 (ADS1256 only)

0011 = AIN3 (ADS1256 only)

0100 = AIN4 (ADS1256 only)

0101 = AIN5 (ADS1256 only)

0110 = AIN6 (ADS1256 only)

0111 = AIN7 (ADS1256 only)

1xxx = AINCOM (when PSEL3 = 1, PSEL2, PSEL1, PSEL0 are "don't care")

NOTE: When using an ADS1255 make sure to only select the available inputs.

Bits 3-0 **NSEL3, NSEL2, NSEL1, NSEL0**: Negative Input Channel (AIN_N) Select

0000 = AIN0

0001 = AIN1 (default)

0010 = AIN2 (ADS1256 only)

0011 = AIN3 (ADS1256 only)

0100 = AIN4 (ADS1256 only)

0101 = AIN5 (ADS1256 only)

0110 = AIN6 (ADS1256 only)

0111 = AIN7 (ADS1256 only)

1xxx = AINCOM (when NSEL3 = 1, NSEL2, NSEL1, NSEL0 are "don't care")

NOTE: When using an ADS1255 make sure to only select the available inputs.

To read 4 differential signals, following commands have to be set:

```
// Get data Channel 1 - Differential: AinP = AIN0, AinN = AIN1 -> p | n -> 0000 0001
unsigned char databyte[6] = {(CMD_WREG | REG_MUX), '\x00', (unsigned char) (0 << 4 | 1),
CMD_SYNC, CMD_WAKEUP, CMD_RDATA};
```

```
// Get data Channel 2 - Differential: AinP = AIN2, AinN = AIN3 -> p | n -> 0010 0011
unsigned char databyte[6] = {(CMD_WREG | REG_MUX), '\x00', (unsigned char) (2 << 4 | 3),
CMD_SYNC, CMD_WAKEUP, CMD_RDATA};
```

```
// Get data Channel 3 - Differential: AinP = AIN4, AinN = AIN5 -> p | n -> 0100 0101
unsigned char databyte[6] = {(CMD_WREG | REG_MUX), '\x00', (unsigned char) (4 << 4 | 5),
CMD_SYNC, CMD_WAKEUP, CMD_RDATA};
```

```
// Get data Channel 4 - Differential: AinP = AIN6, AinN = AIN7 -> p | n -> 0110 0111
unsigned char databyte[6] = {(CMD_WREG | REG_MUX), '\x00', (unsigned char) (6 << 4 | 7),
CMD_SYNC, CMD_WAKEUP, CMD_RDATA};
```

```
write(spiHandle, databyte, 6);
```

9. Conclusions

Some issues raised during testing and integration of those sensors.

- Sensor signals presented some noise peaks. For this reason, a redesign was needed for the board: a filter was added, which improved signal quality.
- Sensor signals were acquired with a raspberry pi board and an ADC/DAC Hat Board. Acquired measurements presented an offset. This error still needs to be investigated.

Due to time limitations, it was decided to postpone the integration of those sensors in a future project and continue using SBG sensor to proceed with testing of control strategies for the platform.